

Research

MICROSTRUCTURE AND CORROSION ANALYSIS OF RRA HEAT TREATED AA7075-T6 TEMPERED ALUMINIUM ALLOY

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Abstract: RRA heat treatment has improved the strength and corrosion resistance of AA7075 composite. The conditions of RRA heat treatment are optimized. In this paper, the optimized heat treatment parameters were found by performing different analyzes. Corrosion resistance and Strength of AA7075 composite were evaluated from the tensile test, hardness test, EDS, and SEM. From the results, we concluded that the parameters which improved the strength and corrosion resistance of AA7075 composite include preaging at 120 °C for 24 h, retrogression at 210 °C for 8 min, and reaging at 120 °C for 24 h.

Keywords: Aluminium alloy AA7075, retrogression and reaging, hardness, mechanical properties, tensile strength, microstructure, corrosion resistance, precipitate behavior, RRA heat treatment

Introduction

Aluminium and its alloys mainly the 7xxx series are one of the most essential metals in the world and broadly used in numerous industries such as aerospace, defense, automotive and military industries due to their high strength, excellent corrosion resistance, low density, lightweight, secure processing and similar other superior mechanical properties [1-9]. The demand for the corrosion resistance and strength of AA7075 alloy has been increased with the advancement of the space field, especially in the industries where weight matters [10].

Even though the mechanical properties of aluminium alloys are better, but their weak corrosion resistance limits their uses, but we can improve their properties by different heat treatment methods such as RRA [2, 11-13]. Even though we can gain the highest strength in AA7075 after the T6 heat treatment [14], but its corrosion resistance and plasticity decrease simultaneously. Similarly, we can increase the corrosion resistance of AA7075 by T7 treatment, but its strength is decreased by 10%-15% [15, 16]. To improve both the mechanical strength and the corrosion resistance at the same time, we use a heat treatment known as retrogression and reaging (RRA) [17-20].

Plasticity, stress corrosion cracking (SCC), exfoliation cracking, and intergranular corrosion (IGC) can decrease the properties of the alloy [21]. Multi-step aging of AA7075 is better than single-step aging [22-25], and it can also increase the SCC resistance [26]. Many previous studies show that after the RRA heat treatment of AA7075, behaviors of the stress corrosion cracking (SCC), exfoliation corrosion (EXCO), and intergranular corrosion (IGC) changes [23, 27, 28].

RRA is a multistep heat treatment process, and we use the material in the T6 condition. RRA heat treatment has three steps; preaging, retrogression, and reaging. RRA treatment has many requirements. The optimization of the RRA treatment process is also very complicated. The corrosion resistance of AA7075 is decided from the pattern of the precipitates at the grain boundary. The precipitates at the grain boundary mostly rely on the aging process. The precipitation-hardening process of the AA7075 composite is a significant subject. The precipitation sequence is generally received as [29-38].

Supersaturated solid solution (α) \rightarrow GP zones (spherical) \rightarrow metastable phase (η') \rightarrow equilibrium phase (η).

Many ultra-fine η' are precipitated in the matrix. The coarse and rough precipitates are accelerated at the grain boundaries. During the retrogression treatment, the size of the precipitates increases [39]. Previous studies show that tensile strength has been increased by the finely distributed matrix precipitates, and the corrosion resistance has been increased by the large precipitate free zones and isolated grain boundary precipitates [40]. The finely dispersed matrix precipitates of RRA samples are the same as that of the T6 samples, but the isolated grain boundary precipitates are more rough and distributed non-homogenously [41].

The complete evaluation of all the parameters is mandatory to optimize the RRA treatment. Previous studies show that improved corrosion resistance and strength are obtained from optimized

parameters. In this work, the investigation of the strength and corrosion resistance of the AA7075-T6 tempered alloy is conducted at different retrogression times and temperatures.

Materials and method

In this work, a 2mm thick T6 tempered AA7075 aluminium alloy was used. Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the material used in experimental studies. Firstly, the T6 tempered alloy is pre-aged again in T6 conditions (120 °C, 24h), then the samples were cooled down to ambient temperature.

Table 1: The chemical composition of the AA7075 alloy used in experimental studies.

Elements	Series Type	Apparent concentration	K ratio	wt%	wt% Sigma	Manufacturer's Standard
C	K-series	0.23	0.00231	9.41	0.34	Yes
O	K-series	0.36	0.00121	1.27	0.08	Yes
Mg	K-series	1.20	0.00795	2.41	0.04	Yes
Al	K-series	38.22	0.27447	78.39	0.33	Yes
Cr	K-series	0.06	0.00064	0.17	0.04	Yes
Fe	K-series	0.08	0.00077	0.20	0.05	Yes
Cu	L-series	0.61	0.00612	1.90	0.10	Yes
Zn	L-series	2.02	0.02019	6.25	0.09	Yes
Total:				100.00		

RRA treatment was carried out according to the conditions shown in Table no. 2.

Table 2: RRA parameters of T6 tempered material

Retrogression			Reaging	
Temperature (°C)	Time (min)	Cooling time (sec)	Temperature (°C)	Time (hr)
200, 205, 210	6, 8, 10, 12	30	120	24

The hardness measurement of the alloys was conducted using a Digital micro hardness tester. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) was used for microstructure examinations and fractured surfaces.

Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the SEM images of AA7075 alloys at the retrogression temperatures of 200 °C, 205 °C, and 210 °C, respectively, using four different retrogression times.

Figure 1: SEM images of AA7075 alloys using different retrogression temperatures and times: a_200 °C-6 min, b_200 °C-8 min, c_200 °C-10 min, d_200 °C-12 min, e_205 °C-6 min, f_205 °C-8 min, g_205 °C-10 min, h_205 °C-12 min, i_210 °C-6 min, j_210 °C-8 min, k_210 °C-10 min, l_210 °C-12 min respectively.

As shown in the SEM images of the AA7075 alloys using different retrogression times and temperatures, the secondary phase precipitates ($MgZn_2$) were formed in the structure as anticipated. Furthermore, the precipitates formed in the structure were not very clear in the

SEM images because they were very small sized precipitates. Figure 2 shows the EDS analysis results of AA7075 alloy for 8 min at 210 ° C.

Figure 2: EDS results of the alloy at 210 °C for 8 min

Previous studies show that the precipitation series of the Al-Zn-Mg-Cu alloys usually exist as supersaturated solid melt, GP zones, η' phase, and stable η phase ($MgZn_2$) [29, 42].

Figure 3 shows the hardness changes of the alloys at different retrogression times and temperatures.

Figure 3: Hardness changes of the composites at different retrogression times and temperatures.

The first decrease in the hardness is interconnected with the starting of dissolving of GP zones and η' phase. A re-expansion of hardness can also be seen because of the forming of a new η' stage over the dissolved GP zones. The η' phase transforms into a stable η phase. The highest hardness value of (190.3 HV) was observed for the alloy at 210 °C for 8 min. This incoherent phase is the reason for the decline of hardness again [43-48].

In the 7xxx series alloys, the strength improvement usually depends on the type, intensity, and size of the precipitates formed in the structure as a result of the heat treatment [49]. Also, stable precipitates ($MgZn_2$) and metastable precipitates ($MgZn_2$) are usually spherical particles that are not easily distinguishable from each other [50]. The maximum tensile strength was obtained for the alloy at 210 °C for 8 min. These results indicate that the tensile strength results supported the hardness results because the increase in the tensile strength of the 7xxx series alloys is achieved by stable $MgZn_2$ precipitates formed in the structure [51, 52].

Conclusion

The RRA parameters of AA7075 alloy are optimized. The results of the tests are calculated. Different analyzes find the best heat-treatment process parameters. The following results were concluded.

- 1) The optimized parameters of the RRA treatment are the most helping parameters in the improvement of the strength and corrosion resistance of the composite.
- 2) Fine matrix precipitates were produced from the optimized parameters of RRA treatment (210 °C for 8 min).
- 3) RRA treatment including preaging at 120 °C for 24 h, retrogression at 210 °C for 8 min, and reaging at 120 °C for 24 h resulted in a suitable coalition of enhancement of both the strength and corrosion resistance simultaneously. The highest hardness value (190.3 HV) was obtained.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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